

Clustering the Four Gospels in the Greek, Latin, Gothic and Old Church Slavonic Translations

Gabriele Cantaluppi, Marco Passarotti

Abstract We present an unsupervised and data-driven comparison of the four Gospels in their versions in four Indoeuropean languages: Greek, Latin, Old Church Slavonic and Gothic. Our method is based on lemmatised and syntactically annotated full texts and provides a lexical- and syntax-based comparison of the texts, by applying clustering and factor analysis techniques. Our results show the high degree of similarity of the different versions on the basis of the regularity of the translations.

Key words: Gospels, Hierarchical Clustering Analysis, Contribution Biplots

1 Introduction

It is a well known fact that three of the four Gospels in the New Testament (namely, those of Luke, Mark and Matthew) are similar to each other and differ from the Gospel of John. This is the reason why they are called the 'synoptic' Gospels, as they report events in a parallel fashion, while John deviates from the narration provided by the others.

This paper wants to provide a lexical- and syntax-based comparison of the four Gospels, by applying clustering and factor analysis techniques on their versions in Greek, Latin, Old Church Slavonic and Gothic. In particular, the paper aims to evaluate the degree of similarity of the different versions on the basis of the regularity of the translations.

Gabriele Cantaluppi

Dipartimento di Scienze statistiche, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Milano, e-mail: gabriele.cantaluppi@unicatt.it

Marco Passarotti

Centro Interdisciplinare di Ricerche per la Computerizzazione dei Segni dell'Espressione, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Milano, e-mail: marco.passarotti@unicatt.it

2 Data and Method

The lemmatised and syntactically annotated texts of the four Gospels in their versions in Greek, Latin, Old Church Slavonic and Gothic were made available recently by the PROIEL corpus¹. We apply clustering and factor analysis techniques to each version of the Gospels in the different languages and, then, we compare the results, in order to evaluate the degree of regularity of the translations².

All the experiments were performed with the R statistical software. In particular, we apply the 'tm' package [2] to build and analyse the document-term matrices.

Clustering We use clustering in order to study the relations of similarity/dissimilarity between the four Gospels in each of the translations considered.

In particular, we perform two kinds of experiments, as we compare the texts by computing their distance in terms of similarity of the relative frequency of (a) the shared lemmas and (b) the syntactic functions³.

This means that texts that share a high number of lemmas with similar distribution and texts that feature a similar distribution of syntactic functions are considered to have a high degree of similarity and, thus, fall into the same or related clusters. For each translation, the analysis starts from the document-term matrix, \mathbf{X} , and builds clusters from the four rows of \mathbf{X} (each row corresponds to one Gospel).

Each row was first divided by its total to obtain relative frequencies and, thus, overcome the different size of the four texts concerned while clustering. A distance based on correlations was considered, by using a complete linkage hierarchical clustering method.

Factor Analysis While the clustering task computes and represents the similarity/dissimilarity value between the texts by clusters, it does not inform about which features distinguish one text from the other. These features are those properties that make two texts similar or dissimilar to each other.

Accordingly to the two kinds of experiments mentioned above, the features that we considered are lemmas and syntactic functions. In order to know which lemmas and syntactic functions distinguish one (or more) Gospel(s) from the other(s) in the different translations, we apply a factor analysis technique.

We compare the distribution of the features in the different translations by using a vector-based representation that results from factor analysis. The degree of similarity/dissimilarity between such representations corresponds to the degree of regularity of the translations.

¹ <http://www.hf.uio.no/ifikk/english/research/projects/proiel>.

² Among the huge amount of publications on (and approaches to) computing textual similarity, here we just report a few citations taken from the Proceedings of the recently held conference SEM-2012 and refer to them for further bibliography [1, 4].

³ While comparing the texts by lemmas, we excluded the function words by exploiting the PoS tagging provided by the morphological annotation of PROIEL (adverbs, articles, conjunctions, prepositions, pronouns). This reduced the size of the data of 50% on average in all the versions of the texts concerned. The resulting number of terms was respectively 2,506 for Latin, 2,807 for Greek, 2,167 for Gothic and 2,693 for Old Church Slavonic.

We follow the Principal Component Analysis biplots presentation by [3], p. 67, and produce 'contribution biplots'. Starting from an $I \times J$ term-document matrix, \mathbf{Y} (whose values had been previously standardised by column, in order to give the same importance to all documents), a reduction of the column space can be achieved by using Factor Analysis and considering factors which relate documents that feature high correlation in their standardised term distributions. The highest correlation occurs when two documents with the same profiles are concerned ('conditional' distributions of terms): in this case, the standardised distributions would result the same. In the opposite case, if two texts do not share any term, the corresponding standardised columns will have a negative correlation.

A weighted singular value decomposition (SVD) of $\mathbf{Y}/(IJ)^{1/2}$ is then performed

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{Y}/(IJ)^{1/2} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{D}_\beta\mathbf{V}'$$

where \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} are matrices containing respectively the left and right singular vectors and \mathbf{D}_β is a diagonal matrix containing the singular values in decreasing order. The SVD allows the calculation of coordinates \mathbf{U} for terms and $\mathbf{G} = J^{1/2}\mathbf{V}\mathbf{D}_\beta$ for documents. By considering the first two columns of \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{G} , we have the coordinates with respect to the first two principal components (orthogonal factors).

The square of the elements in \mathbf{D}_β divided by their total inform about the amount of variance explained by the principal components. In all situations, we observed that the first component alone is able to explain over 90% of the variance.

By considering the squared values of the coordinates of terms we obtain their contribution to the principal axes.

3 Results and Discussion

Clustering It is not surprising that the Gospel of John is clustered apart from the three synoptic ones by both the lexical- and syntax-based analyses applied on all the translations concerned. What differs from one language to the others is the way the synoptic Gospels are clustered. Indeed, two of them are always clustered together against the third, but the most similar couple of Gospels does not remain the same in all the translations.

The most frequent configuration of clusters is such that the couple formed by the Gospels of Luke and Matthew belongs to one cluster separated from that of the Gospel of Mark. This configuration results from both the lexical-based and the syntax-based analysis of the Greek and Latin translations, and from the syntax-based analysis of the Gothic and Old Church Slavonic ones.

A few exceptions to this mainstream configuration do hold. Namely, they are the lexical-based analysis of (a) the Gothic translation, where the couple is formed by the Gospels of Luke and Mark, and (b) the Old Church Slavonic translation, according to which the texts of Mark and Matthew are separated from that of Luke. However, among these two exception, the latter is the only really meaningful one,

as the Gothic translation of the Gospel of Matthew is incomplete and this may influence the analysis.

The high degree of similarity between Luke and Matthew that we observed confirms the standard theory about the problem of the source relationships between the synoptic Gospels. This is a two-source hypothesis, according to which the origin of the Greek text of both Matthew and Luke (written between 80 and 90 CE) are the Gospel of Mark (~ 70 CE) and one hypothetical Sayings Source, usually referred to as the Q source (from German *Quelle*, i.e. 'source').

Factor Analysis According to the above results, only one factor should be extracted in all instances, as the amount of variance explained by the first dimension is always higher than 90%. Nevertheless, we decided to consider also a second factor, as it is able to characterise small (but meaningful) differences among the Gospels, although its amount of explained variance is always lower than 4%.

The percentage values of variability explained by the two factors are almost the same when the texts in Greek (0.943, 0.032), Latin (0.959, 0.023) and Old Church Slavonic (0.955, 0.021) are concerned. These values are slightly different for the Gothic translation (0.925, 0.037).

We observed that the overall distribution of lemmas is much similar in all the languages. In particular, the lemmas that mean *father*, *Jesus*, *jew*, *man*, *to believe*, *to know* and *world* occur in similar positions in all the figures.

However, there is a number of differences, which we resume in the following:

- the lemmas that mean *to make/to do* occur in pretty different positions in Greek and Latin;
- the position of the lemmas that mean *to be* and *to say* is much similar in Greek and Gothic and it is different from that in Latin and Old Church Slavonic;
- the lemma *to come* occurs in the same position in Greek, Latin and Old Church Slavonic, while it is slightly displaced in Gothic;
- the lemmas that mean *house*, *to see* and *to say* in Latin (*domus*, *video*, *aio*) and Old Church Slavonic (домъ, видѣти, рещи) appear in similar position, but they are missing in the figures of Greek and Gothic. The same holds for the lemmas that mean *day* in Gothic (dags) and Old Church Slavonic (днь).

The distribution of syntactic functions is similar in all the versions of the Gospels.

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